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FTT:Agriculture – Model description

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Abstract

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Part I

Theory and computational model

1. Description of the theoretical model

The land allocation model will calculate the supply of agricultural commodities given a supply of land resources, and will simulate land conversions that are incentivised by a commodity price context. We describe here the main equations of this model in a compact way – this is to be formalised later into a real model to be used computationally.

1.1. Land supply

Before we look into land conversions, we may consider how a supply of commodities is achieved using a supply of land resources. The supply of land within a geographical area is composed of diverse plots of land, that we consider allocated for specific agricultural purposes, with particular productivities for different crop types, as well as natural areas that do not produce any crops. Within agricultural land, a certain amount will be used and a certain proportion will be at rest. Our central assumption will be that short term changes in demand for agricultural commodities, since they cannot be met by land conversions rapidly, will be met by changes in the amount of rest land, and therefore that there exists a certain amount of ‘spare capacity’.

Meanwhile the economy will demand a certain amount of agricultural commodities according to the prices people have to pay, and is able to shift its demand depending on absolute and relative prices according to price and cross-price elasticities evaluated econometrically. Thus, to a certain set of prices P_i will be associated a certain set of demands D_i , where the demand of each commodity depends on its price *and* the price of every other substitutable commodity with the set P_i , according to elasticities λ_i and elasticities of substitution λ_{ij} . In other words, for n commodities, $D_i = D_i(P_1, P_2, \dots, P_i, \dots, P_n)$. Since these are considerations at the level of the *consumer* and this model concerns the *producers*, we consider this part as external to FTT:Agriculture and part of E3ME’s material consumption module.¹

Starting from a certain fixed land allocation, the system has a potential supply of agricultural commodities \tilde{G}_i (in units of tonnes t of produce per year, t/y). This potential supply stems from a supply of land suitably allocated for the purpose U_i (in km²), which itself has an average productivity $\bar{\eta}_i$ (in t/y-km²). This actual productivity is composed of a biophysical theoretical potential $v_{i,p}$ and a management factor $MF_{i,p}$ for geographical grid point p , and the productivity averaged over a geographical region is²

$$\bar{\eta}_i = \frac{\sum_p v_{i,p} MF_{i,p} U_{i,p}}{\sum_p U_{i,p}}, \quad U_i = \sum_p U_{i,p} \quad (1)$$

As we explain in section 1.4, while we will obtain from LPJml information on productivity for each of its grid points, we are not likely to obtain information for $MF_{i,p}$ that is resolved in this way, and thus we must replace it by an average over a geographical region \overline{MF}_i .³ In this configuration, we can also define an average biophysical productivity \bar{v}_i , and $\bar{\eta}_i = \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i$.

This explains the ‘productivity gap’, concerning among other things the level of use of fertilisers, irrigation and machinery. Thus we have

$$\tilde{G}_i = U_i \bar{\eta}_i = U_i \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i. \quad (2)$$

The potential supply \tilde{G} is higher than the actual supply, which is itself equal to the demand $G_i \equiv D_i$ (by construction: the demand is exogenous to FTT:Agri and is determined by E3ME). Before allowing for land conversions, there is no reason for which \tilde{G}_i should be equal or closely related to G_i since demand fluctuations occur for reasons unrelated to the land supply; thus a certain amount of spare land exists, which farmers use to buffer short term changes in demand. Naturally, the land that is most expensive to farm is kept at rest for these purposes, i.e. we assume land with lowest productivity (e.g. hillsides).

¹Note that this is identical to how FTT:Power functions, where the demand for electricity is calculated by E3ME while the power mix is calculated by FTT.

²This average can apply either when using the model at the national level or when re-aggregating to a coarser grid resolution.

³This is fairly reasonable considering that it is closely tied to levels of economic development, which often depends more strongly on national levels of income rather than highly resolved geographical location.

Figure 1:

We define the ratio between potential supply, where no rest land exists, to the actual supply, as the land use factor ϕ_i ,

$$G_i = \phi_i U_i \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i, \quad \frac{G_i}{\bar{G}_i} = \phi_i. \quad (3)$$

The sector responds to short term changes in demand D_i with changes in ϕ_i . However in the longer term, the land use factor ϕ_i can be altered if more land becomes available for a particular purpose, if the management factor changes (e.g. buying tractors) and if the theoretical productivity of the land changes (e.g. changes in water availability). This can be expressed using a differential form,

$$\phi_i = \frac{G_i}{U_i \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i}, \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta\phi_i = \frac{1}{U_i \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i} \Delta G_i - \frac{G_i}{U_i^2 \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i} \Delta U_i - \frac{G_i}{U_i \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i} \Delta \overline{MF}_i - \frac{G_i}{U_i \overline{MF}_i \bar{v}_i^2} \Delta \bar{v}_i, \quad (5)$$

Here, the first term corresponds to short term changes in demand, the second corresponds to changes in allocation, the third to changes in management level and the fourth to changes in biophysical properties of the land. These can all change simultaneously or in subgroups. If for example the change in land use factor is nil, one or more of the other changes must cancel each other out (e.g. reducing supply of land due to increasing productivity and or demand, etc). Another example is if land conversions are not allowed and that land productivities are constant, then changes in short term demand must be accommodated by changes in the management factor and the land use factor (intensification).

The use of the land is most efficient the closer ϕ_i is to 1. However there is no good argument to support that ϕ should be maximal at all times, especially given the fact that changes in demand occur at all time scales (changes occur at all possible frequencies) for reasons unrelated to the supply of land (further discussed in section ???). The

Figure 2: Illustration of the determination of the marginal cost C_{max} . Given the distribution land available at fixed allocation for one particular crop, a fraction smaller than the total amount will actually be used for production, with a remaining amount left at rest. The land with lowest productivity and highest production cost is assumed to determine the marginal cost of production (left panel). This marginal cost is larger than the average cost \bar{C} . $\bar{\sigma}$ is the standard deviation. On the right panel, we give the same illustration using a cost-supply curve, which is the inverse of the cumulative cost distribution. Here again, the demand determines the marginal cost of production.

differential equation can also be expressed in terms of rates of change:

$$\frac{\Delta\phi_i}{\phi_i} = \frac{\Delta G_i}{G_i} - \frac{\Delta U_i}{U_i} - \frac{\Delta \overline{MF}_i}{\overline{MF}_i} - \frac{\Delta \bar{v}_i}{\bar{v}_i}. \quad (6)$$

1.2. Commodity prices

The production of agricultural commodities requires the use of land with different actual productivities. Different productivities, in units of tonnes per year-square kilometre (t/y-km²), lead to different levels of human effort to produce the same amount, imply different costs of production, where the least productive plot will have the highest cost. For individual plots of land, numbered p , within a geographical area k (figure 1), this is approximately

$$C_{i,p} = C_{i,p}^0 + \frac{C_{i,p}^1}{\eta_{i,p}} = C_{i,p}^0 + \frac{C_{i,p}^1}{v_{i,p} \overline{MF}_i}, \quad (7)$$

where $C_{i,p}^1$ refers to all fixed costs that apply per land area, such as land rental, while $C_{i,p}^0$ refers to all variable costs that apply per tonne produced, such as transport, fuel, labour and operation of machinery. These values can be inferred from data (see fig ???), where they were obtained by fitting total costs against productivity using this equation form. It is not really possible to obtain such cost values per plot of land, however it is possible to obtain regional estimates. While the rent or value of the land might change locally, differences are likely larger across countries [?] due to, for instance, exchange rates or levels of income. Meanwhile, wages and transport costs are mostly defined regionally, not by plot of land. The same applies also to the management factor, which is a measure of technological development. Thus it is not a bad approximation to use constants nation-wide for $C_{i,p}^0$, $C_{i,p}^1$ and \overline{MF}_i , and assume that local variations are primarily driven by differences in productivity:

$$C_{i,p} = C_i^0 + \frac{C_i^1}{\eta_{i,p}} = C_i^0 + \frac{C_i^1}{v_{i,p} \overline{MF}_i}, \quad \eta_{i,p} = v_{i,p} \overline{MF}_i \quad (8)$$

In order to determine prices, we take our central model assumption that a certain commodity demand is met by G_i , at fixed allocation, which is lower than the potential supply \tilde{G}_i . Allocation changes take place at a slower pace with delay, and thus do not participate here. If farmers use for this purpose their land with highest productivity, but that land productivities within the current allocation of land are distributed then it may be the case that crops of that

type produced that had production costs below the commodity price (minus some possible markups from possible intermediate agents), yielding a positive profit value $\pi_i = P_i - C_i$, are sold, up to the point of zero profit, and those that had production costs higher than the price are not sold (and ignored by us). In such a case, the productivity of the plot of land with zero profit determines the marginal cost, and has the lowest productivity in the set that is required by the demand. The price of the commodity will be function of the marginal cost, since the formation of the price is not possible until a deal is struck on the sale of the most expensive unit. In a fixed land allocation, this price will thus vary according to the demand, depending on the distribution of productivities, and the demand will depend on the price, depending on the economy and elasticities of substitution.

To formalise this, if the cost distribution for the production of commodity i is $g_i(\sigma_i, C_i - \bar{C}_i)$, with \bar{C}_i the mean of the distribution and σ_i its standard deviation, then the production is

$$D_i \equiv G_i = \int_0^{C_i^{max}} g_i(\sigma_i, C_i - \bar{C}_i) dC_i, \quad (9)$$

which defines the marginal cost C_i^{max} by equating G_i to D_i . This equation, if inverted, is a cost-supply curve, in which we specify a demand value, and it gives us a marginal cost. In other words, if one integrates the cost distribution $g_i(\sigma_i, C_i - \bar{C}_i)$ into a cumulative distribution $G_i(C_i)$, one can then invert the function into a cost function of production (by numerical interpolation since this is a monotonic function), giving a function for the marginal cost $C_i^{max}(G_i)$, the cost of the most expensive plot of land used to produce G_i . This implies that the model can either have a database of cost-supply curves in order to determine the marginal costs used in the calculation of prices, or parameterised inverted cumulative distributions if their form is simple. As we will see later, however, we will have to sum the production from different types of land (irrigated and non-irrigated), and the inversion of a sum of functions is usually not possible analytically. Therefore for this, we will use interpolation through a database of cost-supply curves.⁴

The result of this part of the model is what we have before we allow for land conversions, where the price of agricultural commodities is entirely determined by the distribution of costs, the demand for commodities and which cost value clears the market, the marginal value at which the profit is zero. If the demand increases, less productive land is used, and the price increases. If the demand decreases, some land will be put at rest, the marginal cost will decrease, followed by the price. The amount of land unused corresponds to $(1 - \phi_i)U_i$.

1.3. Land conversions

In situations of high demand, the amount of rest land could decrease to very low values ($1 - \phi_i \rightarrow 0$), implying the use of lower productivity land and high commodity prices. This will incentivise farmers to convert the use of certain numbers of their plots of land in order to capture profit opportunities, generating a higher supply of land to use for this purpose and most likely decreasing the production cost. This higher supply will likely imply a higher supply of higher productivity land allocated to the purpose, which will decrease the land use factor, the marginal cost and thus the price. Thus price signals will generate in the model conversions of the land. However, as in any FTT model, conversions come with a time lag, as this is a dynamical model. While the short term supply is met by adjusting the land use factor, the long term supply is adjusted with time lags by land conversions between types (e.g. cutting down forest).

Land conversions therefore do not take place instantaneously.⁵ It takes time and investment for converting the production of one type of crop to the production of another. For instance, palm oil or fruit production requires a time investment of several years where not output is generated, and thus the conversion of yearly crops to those can only accommodate changes of prices on a timescale of several years. The reverse conversion back to yearly crops may be much faster however. Thus the conversion between any pair j and i of possible crops has an average conversion timescale associated, which we define here as τ_{ij} , and is not symmetrical. It is most unlikely that land is re-converted shortly after conversion before any crop is harvested, since this implies the loss of significant amounts of expected income (and possible default on loans and bankruptcy). Thus it is assumed in this model that farmers wait until harvest

⁴The same is done for renewables energy resources in FTT:Power.

⁵If they did, we could have $G_i = \bar{G}_i$, where conversions accommodate instantaneously changes in demand, and this would be an optimisation model. However conversions take time, times longer than typical fluctuations in demand.

(i.e. a length of time τ_{ij}) before considering any conversions. This therefore means that crops have a life expectancy of τ_{ij} .

Furthermore, farmers are entrepreneurs who, as in business, are trying to make best use of their resources given a changing context. We see the farmer here similarly as an entrepreneur in startup ventures: he makes various business plans for different possible projects, compares them, and chooses which one he thinks it is worth investing in, or borrowing money for. For this, he must make assumptions about what he thinks the future will be (in particular the prices of commodities) and the information that he uses in his planning may or may not be confirmed by real events.

1.3.1. The business plans

We elaborate the farmer's business plan-making further here. In any business plan, entrepreneurs calculate net present values of all incomes and expenditures, and chooses the best option based on a comparison. He will have a view on his own time preference, his discount rate, which is related to his level of income and his access to credit. We do not assume that all decision-makers are trained in business management; however, even in the case of largely illiterate populations, we believe that discount rates exist, which implies that decisions involve some form of discounting of costs and income that are further ahead in the future, and therefore, net present value calculations are appropriate, given that we know approximately which discount rate they effectively use.

Farmers, when considering what to plant on a plot of land, will consider what profit they would make upon the sale of the crop at harvest time. This involves two components, a future price of the commodity, and a future cost of production, both projected by the farmer, to the best of his knowledge, for the time of harvest. The cost of production involves several components, as indicated above, some fixed costs and a cost that depends of the productivity of the land. The land having all sorts of productivities for each type of crop, farmers will take different decisions for individual plots of land depending on their relative productivities. We thus define a levelised cost of production (LCOP), which determines what is the minimum price at which a farmer would have to sell his agricultural produce, of a particular type, if he were to produce it, in order not to lose any money. This is determined by the use of two net present value (NPV) calculations, one for all income, one for all costs.

The business plan works as follows. We calculate NPV of costs in units of dollars per tonne produced,

$$NPV_C = \sum_t \frac{\frac{LR_i(t)}{\eta_i} + \frac{MC_i(t)}{\eta_i} + MM(t) + LW(t) - AS(t) + \dots}{(1+r)^t}, \quad (10)$$

and that of earnings when selling crops at the break-even price in the same units:

$$NPV_E = \sum_t \frac{P_i^{BE}(t)}{(1+r)^t}. \quad (11)$$

Here, some costs are fixed (in dollars per km²), for instance the land rental (LR) and machinery (MC) and thus are divided by the productivity, while others scale with the amount of produce, for instance the management (MM), labour wages (LW) and agricultural subsidies (AS). These expected costs are discounted to the present with discount rate r which depends on to farmers, not crops, and thus may be distributed. All these expected costs are understood as projections for the length of the project made by the farmer at the time of investment, and could turn out wrong, and thus t runs from the time of investment to the time of the sale of the crops. Since projects of different types need to be compared on equal grounds, and that they could have different lengths, they must be normalised by the discounting procedure, which the LCOP enables us to do. $P_i^{BE}(t)$ is the break-even price, or cost of production when all components are considered at the time when they are incurred, which we take as constant. If we equate NPV_C to NPV_E and isolate $P_i^{BE}(t)$, we obtain

$$LCOP_i = P_i^{BE}(t) = \frac{\sum_t \frac{LR_i(t) + \frac{MC_i(t)}{\eta_i} + MM(t) + LW(t) - AS(t) + \dots}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_t \frac{1}{(1+r)^t}}. \quad (12)$$

The normalised present value of expected profits on sale are thus the difference between this cost and the levelised

income derived from the expected price $P_i^{EX}(t)$ of the commodity at the time of sale. We express this here as

$$\pi_i = \frac{\sum_t \frac{P_i^{EX}(t)}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_t \frac{1}{(1+r)^t}} - LCOP_i. \quad (13)$$

This way, projects with any profile of costs and income in time over any time horizon can be compared on equal footing. Note that time t here refers to an imaginary time, in the mind of the farmer when he makes prospective plans. In each case he considers the full life-cycle of costs and income over future imaginary time, and chooses based on which gives the most income per unit of land used. Note that modelling behaviour based on expectations of profits is exactly consistent with the General Theory of [1], where expectations drive the model away from equilibrium, leads to cycles, etc. This is therefore what we expect from this FTT model. Inserting assumptions about expectations into $P_i^{EX}(t)$ will lead to different outcomes.

1.3.2. Decision-making by farmers: aggregating the options

For this model's comparison of options, we want to aggregate the options over geographical regions. We know that over such an area, the productivity η_i varies significantly, and we have as starting data the distributions of productivity from LPJml, aggregated by grouping grid points into a number of geographical areas. Thus if farmers were identical and had identical perceptions of costs and time preference, this equation would nevertheless vary according to the variations of $1/\eta_i$. In this view, since the productivities η_i are distributed for each crop, expected profits π_i are distributed as well. However on top of that, farmers may not have identical perceptions of costs and time preference, and therefore any of the terms and the discount rate r may be distributed. The price, however, is the same for everyone, and thus is not distributed, but its projections based on expectations may differ for different farmers.⁶

Therefore, the widths of distributions are representations of agent diversity, i.e. the diversity of their perceptions. For instance, if we used a distributed discount rate, representing variations in risk perceptions and access to credit, then expected profits would be distributed, even in a case where the productivity was single-valued. This means that for particular context changes, farmer responses would vary and be distributed as well. If any term is distributed in the expression for expected profits, then its expression is

$$\Delta\pi_i = \sqrt{\frac{d\pi_i^2}{d\eta_i^2} \Delta\eta_i + \frac{d\pi_i^2}{dr} \Delta r + \frac{d\pi_i^2}{dLR_i} \Delta LR_i + \frac{d\pi_i^2}{dP_i^{EX}} \Delta P_i^{EX} + \dots} / \left(\sum_t \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} \right), \quad (14)$$

a standard error propagation calculation.⁷ The convenient aspect of this root mean square calculation is that larger variations tend to dominate strongly, which enables us to safely omit variations that we know are small. In this case, at the country level, we consider to first order that variations of productivity 'drown' any other variations. This is definitely not true at other scales however, especially at grid scale, which we will consider later. Beyond variations in productivity, it is likely that variations in the discount rate are dominant, which reflect existing wealth distributions.

1.3.3. Modelling decision-making by groups of farmers: aggregating and comparing

At the agent level, we have a model of cost comparison, which can be solved by a series of pairwise comparison of numbers. At the aggregate level, however, we face comparisons of distributions. Assuming that one knows the parameterisation of the distributions of expected profit in all regions for all crops (considering that if a crop does not grow in a certain region, its productivity is zero and cost infinite, and can thus be ignored), given a certain set of prices P_i , the decision-making model can be defined using pair-wise comparisons of distributed profits π_i . The result of this should be proportions of agents taking various decisions. Where distributions are very narrow, agents are near to identical, and similar decisions should result. Where distributions are broad, results should be divided across the population. This procedure is described in detail in [2]; we reproduce it here.

⁶We do not consider this in this model version as it is not really important in comparison to the other sources of variation.

⁷This can be demonstrated easily by considering that the sum of distributed terms correspond to convolutions of their distributions. The resulting standard deviation corresponds to the sum of the square of the variations, irrespective of the distribution types, as long as a standard deviation can be defined.

Comparing two probability distributions involves counting the relative number of instances (or probability \mathcal{P}) where possible values of expected profits from a crop i turn out higher than profits from crop j . If the probability distributions have average profit values $\bar{\pi}_i$ and $\bar{\pi}_j$, this counting procedure is expressed as follows. First, we calculate the probability of choosing i using arbitrary profit π for j . Our central assumption is that the fraction of decision instances in which the expected profit π_j for j is π and for whom the profit π_i for i is higher than π , will take crop i over j . This fraction of all decisions taken between i and j is equal to the cumulative probability distribution $F_i(\pi - \bar{\pi}_i)$ of standard deviation σ_i . But this situation of profit value π for j occurs a fraction $f_j(\pi - \bar{\pi}_j)$ of the time, with standard deviation σ_j . The combined probability distribution for any value of π is therefore

$$\mathcal{P}(\pi_i > \pi | \pi = \pi_j) d\pi = (1 - F_i(\pi - \bar{\pi}_i)) f_j(\pi - \bar{\pi}_j) d\pi, \quad (15)$$

while the reverse reasoning gives

$$\mathcal{P}(\pi_j > \pi | \pi = \pi_i) d\pi = (1 - F_j(\pi - \bar{\pi}_j)) f_i(\pi - \bar{\pi}_i) d\pi. \quad (16)$$

In order to know how often the profit from crop i is higher than that of crop j , and the converse, we must sum over all possible values of π . For simplicity, we make a change of variables $\pi' = \pi - \bar{\pi}_j$ and $\pi'' = \pi - \bar{\pi}_i$, with the mean cost difference $\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij} = \bar{\pi}_i - \bar{\pi}_j$,

$$F_{ij}(\Delta\pi_{ij}) = \mathcal{P}(\pi_i > \pi_j) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - F_i(\pi' - \Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij})) f_j(\pi') d\pi', \quad (17)$$

$$F_{ji}(\Delta\pi_{ji}) = \mathcal{P}(\pi_j > \pi_i) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - F_j(\pi'' + \Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij})) f_i(\pi'') d\pi''. \quad (18)$$

These integrals appear difficult to evaluate without knowing the distribution type. In particular, for instance, this is difficult to calculate if the f are normal distributions. However one may simplify the integrals by calculating their derivative with respect to the average profit difference $\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}$:

$$\frac{dF_{ij}}{d\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}} = - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_i(\pi'' - \Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}) f_j(\pi'') d\pi'' = -f_{ij}(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}), \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{dF_{ji}}{d\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_j(\pi' + \Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}) f_i(\pi') d\pi' = f_{ji}(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}). \quad (20)$$

These are convolutions of the probability distributions, which are normally straightforward to calculate, either analytically or numerically. In fact, the convolution of two normal distributions corresponds simply to the addition of the two distributions. If their standard deviations are σ_i and σ_j , their convolution is a normal distribution of standard deviation $\sigma_{ij} = \sqrt{\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_j^2}$. Actually, this addition of standard deviations σ is true for any type of distribution, however the addition of two-non normal distributions *is not* a distribution of the same type.⁸

By symmetry (interchanging the distributions in the convolution) we must have that $f_{ij}(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}) = f_{ji}(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij})$. Thus by integrating again these results along $\Delta\pi_{ij}$, one obtains that

$$F_{ji} = 1 - F_{ij}, \quad (21)$$

which is self-consistent, indicating that the choice is exclusive. F_{ij} is thus a cumulative probability distribution of width σ_{ij} , the sum of the squares of the individual standard deviations for any type of probability distribution, assuming that they have only one mode. This, in the language of discrete choice theory, is a binary logit model.

The standard assumption in discrete choice theory is to assume that the data follows a Gumbel distribution, of which the convolution with itself gives a logistic distribution [see for instance 3]. In this work we do not bother with

⁸Only the gaussian function possesses this property that when convolved with itself it results in another gaussian.

determining the type of distribution; we assume that they are of the Gumbel type and that the combined distribution $f_{ij}(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij})$ is of the logistic type of width σ_{ij} , of which the cumulative distribution F_{ij} is a logistic function.⁹

The combined distributions $f_{ij}(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij})$ and $f_{ji}(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij})$ tell where, in terms of profit difference $\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}$ between crop i and crop j , conversion decisions are probable. If $|\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}|$ is very large (positive or negative) in comparison to σ_{ij} , it is clear which crop should dominate and no change of choice takes place. If however $|\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij}|$ is near to or less than σ_{ij} , then significant numbers of decisions for conversion (although not necessarily actual conversions) are expected to take place, from the lower to the higher profit value. Thus when prices change, if the value of profits cross, conversions take place towards the higher profit, following a logistic curve, at a rate that is determined by the standard deviation of the combined distribution σ_{ij} .

1.3.4. On project lifetimes

Agricultural projects, as we've seen above, have a lifetime. Various costs and earnings take place at various times during their varying life cycles. One aspect however constrains farmers when they take decisions: the allocation of resources. If, for instance, a farmer borrows money in order to carry out a project, it is likely that the time over which he repays his loan constrains his future decisions, until the time when his resource are freed again, at which point he can take another loan and so on. In the mean time, he is bound by law to repay his debts. In this model, we tie the loan to the project and assume that the farmer is bound by law to carry out his project to the end in order to repay his loans: we do not allow early scrapping of projects. An example of early scrapping would be a farmer who borrows money for a forestry project, plants trees, and later converts the land for another use before the trees are harvested. In this case, he loses the income that he assumed would be used to repay his loan and make a profit. This is possible in reality, but we may treat this separately in the future; however since it involves a loss, there is a strong incentive to avoid such situations.

We define the lifetime τ_i of a type of project as the time after conversion under which a farmer would not be ready to re-convert his land for another purpose. It is related to how quickly he can recover his resources in order to invest in a new project. This lifetime is not necessarily related to the time to harvest, where especially in the case of yearly crops, it is not reasonable to assume that farmers would be willing to convert their land every year. Project lifetimes can depend on which types of alternate projects are considered, and thus we will denote them with two indices τ_{ij} .

1.3.5. The conversions

Crop conversions can happen for all sorts of reasons, and in particular, some conversions could take place between one type j to another i , simultaneously to elsewhere where the reverse conversion takes place from type i to type j . This could be due for instance to widely distributed productivity values. We define here the proportion of land supply dedicated to crop i , U_i , to the total land supply U_{tot} . The amount of land that can be converted from type j to type i depends on the existing amount of land dedicated to crop j , but only a proportion of it can be converted, depending on whether it is ready given the time it takes to carry out the whole life cycle of an agricultural project; in other words a fraction $1/\tau_{ij}$ of U_j . However, some plots of land suitable for crop j may not be suitable for crop i ¹⁰. Thus we must subtract the amount of land unsuitable for the conversion, which we may denote U_{ij}^0 (the amount of land suitable for crop j unsuitable for crop i). This is illustrated in figure 3.

A critical assumption of this model is that the growth of a new type of crop within a certain geographical area most likely depends on the number of plots of land already dedicated to this use. This could stem simply from the availability of seeds, which itself depends on the amount of the same crop, but most likely also on a human tendency to wait for observing the success of other farmers before venturing into something new. A completely new type of crop would most likely be tried at small scale by a small number of farmers, before being adopted upon success by a larger number of farmers. This can be interpreted as a lack of universal knowledge by farmers, and/or lack of universal access to seeds, where particular farming habits replicate themselves by their widespread use. Thus by this we argue that the growth of a particular crop type depends on its own proportion of land use. We will see later that this has very important implications to the behaviour of the model, which is made significantly more realistic in this way.

⁹The difference between the normal and logistic distributions is very small, the logistic distribution having slightly 'fatter' tails. This choice of distribution significantly simplifies the analysis.

¹⁰Actually, it may be the case sometimes that for some biophysical reason, no land suitable for a particular crop j (e.g. rice) is suitable for crop i (e.g. wheat).

Figure 3: Illustration of the suitability of land areas for conversions between an arbitrary pair of crop types i and j . Some land areas will be only suitable for type i (blue squares with blue borders) while some will only be suitable for type j (red squares with red borders). These, having zero productivity for the alternate crop type, do not participate to the conversion process and need to be taken out from the calculation, and correspond to the quantity U_{ij}^0 in eq. 26. Some areas will be suitable for both types but will be dominated by one type (blue or red squares with mixed colour borders), while some areas will be mixed (mixed colour squares with mixed colour borders). These all participate to the conversion process according to their relative productivities. Note that any of these areas may or not be suitable for, and be used for another third crop type, say k , but this is taken account for when the same calculation is carried out for the pairs i, k and j, k .

Finally, we can formalise the choice of farmers between all possible pairs of possible crops as a distributed function, described in section ??, denoted there as F_{ij} . Given a choice between crop i and crop j , this gives the proportion of plots of land for which farmers would decide to plant crop i , while F_{ji} indicates the number of these over which farmers would decide to plant crop j . This choice being exclusive, it means that $F_{ij} + F_{ji} = 1$. Given this choice and the previous three arguments, the area of land that would become converted from type j to type i , $\Delta U_{j \rightarrow i}$, during a time interval Δt corresponds to (1) the amount of land of type j ready for the conversion, that can be converted to type i (i.e. it has a non-zero productivity for type i), (2) the proportion of this which is chosen by farmers to be converted, F_{ij} , and (3) the proportion of farmers already accustomed to this type of crop, or alternatively, the proportion of land already converted to this type of crop

$$\Delta U_{j \rightarrow i} = \left(\frac{U_j - U_{ij}^0}{\tau_{ij}} \right) (F_{ij}) \left(\frac{U_i - U_{ji}^0}{U_{tot}} \right) \Delta t. \quad (22)$$

Meanwhile, the amount of land that would simultaneously be converted from type i to type j is

$$\Delta U_{i \rightarrow j} = \left(\frac{U_i - U_{ji}^0}{\tau_{ji}} \right) (F_{ji}) \left(\frac{U_j - U_{ij}^0}{U_{tot}} \right) \Delta t \quad (23)$$

The quantity U_{ij}^0 is obtained by counting the number of plots of land of type j that has a zero productivity for type i , which we can denote as

$$U_{ij}^0 = \sum_p \delta(v_{i,p}) (1 - \delta(v_{j,p})), \quad \delta(v_{i,p}) = \begin{cases} 1, & v_{i,p} > 0 \\ 0, & v_{i,p} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

The net exchange of land between categories i and j is thus

$$\Delta U_{ij} = \Delta U_{j \rightarrow i} - \Delta U_{i \rightarrow j}, \quad (25)$$

which can be re-organised and summed over all possible crop type j :

$$\Delta U_i = \frac{1}{U_{tot}} \sum_j (U_i - U_{ji}^0) (U_j - U_{ij}^0) \left(\frac{F_{ij}}{\tau_{ij}} - \frac{F_{ji}}{\tau_{ij}} \right) \Delta t. \quad (26)$$

This is the dynamical equation driving conversions in the model. In this model, conversions take place at a rate which is determined by the physical rate of conversion τ_{ij}^{-1} as well as by decisions of farmers F_{ij} , the latter being

influenced by the price context and their expectations of reaping a profit. This is a modified version of an equation common in the field of evolutionary economics, where it is named a ‘replicator dynamics’ equation, which originates from evolutionary theory in biology. It can be derived exactly from a population growth equation for competing species in biology, called the ‘Lotka-Volterra’ equation.¹¹ It is modified here to allow for some amount of mismatch between the suitability of the land.

Finally, note that the conversion between two land types ΔU_{ij} does not exactly correspond to choices F_{ij} , as even with a clear preference in terms of profits, information or expertise is not necessarily available, and conversions take time. This is expressed by the fact that conversions are proportional to $U_i U_j F_{ij}$, not only F_{ij} . This prevents conversions to take place everywhere simultaneously instantaneously in the event where prices change abruptly, making this temporarily profitable, as might be the case in a model based on pure optimisation. This decouples conversions from the volatility of prices and enables to bring in finite conversion timescales, which slow down the rate of transformation and prevent unrealistic fast fluctuations between land types.¹²

1.4. The management factor: induced technological change

The management factor for the land in each country depends on investment made to improve productivity. This involves both improving farming methods using some R&D investments as well as direct investments in technology such as tractors and machinery, including the use of fertilisers. The amount of investment that should go in improving productivity is somewhat beyond the scope of the model definition of FTT:Agriculture. However, this is already calculated in E3ME through the investment equations, which can then be used here.

In E3ME, technological progress is calculated using cumulated R&D and ordinary investment, by introducing technological progress indicators (TPIs) within the econometric equations, notably in those for trade and prices. The higher the activity in one sector, the more investment takes place for expanding production capacity, the more technology improves, and therefore productivity increases which decreases prices. This is the sources of endogenous economic growth in E3ME. The TPI has the following form:¹³

$$TPI(t) \propto \sum_{a=0}^{\infty} e^{-a\tau_1} \ln(I(t-a) + \tau_2 R\&D(t-a)), \quad (27)$$

The TPI for the agricultural sector can thus also be used for determining the average management factor of the land MF , to which individual management factors must be linked.

1.5. Climate change and the productivity

The potential productivities v_i , to which actual productivities η_i are linked through the management factors MF_i , can change over time if the climate changes. In the broader picture of the E3ME-FTT model linked to emulators of the carbon cycle (GENIEem) and climate system (PLASIM-ENTSem), linked back again to the land use model (LPJml-em), emissions from the global economy can lead to significant climate change and changes of rainfall, which will lead to changes in water availability, used in the calculation of potential productivities in LPJml. This cycle thus must lead to transformations in the way the land is used if no policies are adopted to reduce emissions, and perhaps less so if stringent climate policies are adopted.

In this context, changes of productivities v_i will take place as the simulation runs. While we will not be able to run the emulator simultaneously to E3ME, we will require to iterate the two models until convergence. In this approach, the productivities v_i must be considered as given exogenously. These will changes fairly slowly as the emulator provides decadal values which will need to be interpolated yearly in FTT:Agriculture.

1.6. The representation of policy in FTT:Agriculture

??? To be completed ???

¹¹Note that here, as opposed to other FTT models, the carrying capacity, the total amount of land U_{tot} is a constant, and therefore there is no chain derivative to consider between a differential equation in U_i and one in S_i , simplifying the analysis.

¹²Note in this respect that the model is a continuous time model (differential equations), which is to be approximated using a finite time step. If the time step is too slow, the model can fall into chaotic modes. However this is *always* resolved by using shorter time steps.

¹³ τ_1 plays the role of knowledge depreciation while τ_2 is a weighting parameter for R&D, see [4].

2. How to implement FTT:Agriculture in MATLAB code

To summarise this theory section, we list here all the necessary relationships and operations in correct order of calculation. The model starts with E3ME, which provides a set of demands for agricultural commodities which are functions of the set of prices for those commodities. Since there exist substitution between these commodities, cross-elasticities are present, and thus the demand for one commodity is function of its own price plus the price of all the other commodities, which we denote $D_i = D_i(P_i)$. In principle, E3ME generates these demand values from economic activity according to a set of prices P_i , and FTT:Agriculture determines a set of prices, according to costs of production and the land allocation, given this set of demand values:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \text{Iteration} & 1 & P_i \rightarrow E3ME \rightarrow D_i \\
 & 1 & D_i \rightarrow FTT \rightarrow P'_i \\
 \text{Iteration} & 2 & P'_i \rightarrow E3ME \rightarrow D'_i \\
 & 2 & D'_i \rightarrow FTT \rightarrow P''_i \\
 \text{Iteration} & 3 & P''_i \rightarrow E3ME \rightarrow D''_i \\
 & \dots & \dots
 \end{array} \tag{28}$$

1- Determine the land use factors from the E3ME demand values D_i compared to the biophysical production values from LPJmL

$$\phi_i = \frac{D_i}{\tilde{G}_i}. \tag{29}$$

2- Determine the value of the marginal cost of production for each commodity given the land use factors. At the starting point of the simulation, from data of the emulator of LPJmL, we already have distributions of productivities of the current land allocation, parameterised with an average cost \bar{C}_i and standard deviation $\bar{\sigma}_i$. If we use a logistic distribution for the inverse productivities, then this corresponds to calculating

$$P_i = \alpha_i C_i^{max} = \alpha_i \bar{\sigma}_i \operatorname{arctanh} \phi_i + \bar{C}_i, \quad \phi_i = \frac{D_i}{\tilde{G}_i} \tag{30}$$

3- Determine the distributed net present value of potential projects and their distributed profits

$$\bar{\pi}_i = P_i - \bar{C}_i \tag{31}$$

4- Determine the decision-making for every possible pair of crops $F_{ij} = F(\Delta\bar{\pi}_{ij})$.

5- Determine the conversions

$$\Delta U_i = \frac{1}{U_{tot}} \sum_j (U_i - U_{ji}^0) (U_j - U_{ij}^0) \left(\frac{F_{ij}}{\tau_{ij}} - \frac{F_{ji}}{\tau_{ij}} \right) \Delta t. \tag{32}$$

6- Determine the new biophysical production given possible climate change, productivity changes, management factor changes,

$$\tilde{G}_i = U_i \bar{v}_i \overline{MF}_i. \tag{33}$$

7- Back to determining land use factor changes in step 1.

Part II

Supporting data and methodology

3. Agricultural production cost

The production of agricultural commodities requires the use of land with different actual productivities. Different productivities, in units of tonnes per square kilometre (t/km²), lead to different levels of human efforts to produce the same amount, implies different costs of production, where the least productive plot will have the highest cost. This can be expressed as

$$C_i = C_i^0 + \frac{C_i^1}{\eta_i} = C_i^0 + \frac{C_i^1}{v_i MF_i}, \quad (34)$$

where C_i refers to average cost of production (\$/t), C_i^0 refers to all costs that apply per tonne produced (\$/t), which can be called average variable cost, such as transport, fuel, labour and operation of machinery, while C_i^1 refers to all costs that apply per land area (\$/km²) which can be called fixed cost, such as land rental. This inverse relationship will be explored with survey data from the US and China for four major crops, including rice, wheat, maize and soybean. These survey data provide itemised cost and associated yield from unit land area (which is treated as productivity) for different agricultural zones (US) or major production provinces (China). This productivity refer to η_i , as it is from observation with management applied to v_i originating from biophysical and geographical variations.

The US and China are selected because of the data availability and their representiveness in agricultural structure as developed country and fast-growing country. China survey data cover the period of 2004 to 2012 for all the four crops based on the *Annuals of Cost and Profit of National Agricultural Products*, while US data cover different period dating back as early as 1996 to 2012, based on the survey data of U.S Department of Agriculture (USDA).

When farmers choose the land use type for certain production, the cost of production should be lower than market price to make profits. In the market, commodity price is also affected by production cost. Therefore, change in cost would eventually be reflected in price, and will come from the factors that have large contribution in total cost. The itemised costs in the US and China are different, so they need to be integrated to be comparable. The US survey has classified production costs to *operating costs* and *allocated overhead*. The *operation costs* refer to direct consumption of agricultural materials during production, including seed, fertiliser, chemicals, rent of temporary labour and machinery, fuel, lube and electricity, repairs and interest on operating inputs; *allocated overhead* refer to costs other than operation costs, which are allocated to a production cycle, including hired labour, opportunity cost of unpaid labour, capital recovery of machinery and equipment, rental rate, taxes and insurance and other general management fees.

The sampling data of China have classified costs to three items as *production costs*, *period costs* and *tax*. *Production costs* include material cost and labour cost. Materials include all the direct and indirect input of agricultural materials during production, such as seed, fertiliser, chemicals, plastic sheeting, machinery, irrigation and animal power, fuel, lube and electricity, repair and depreciation of fixed assets. Labour cost include all the direct and in direct input of labour. *Period costs* including land rent, cost induced from management, sale and financial activities. *Tax* includes tax on agriculture, sales and agricultural and forestry specialties.

To make the above-mentioned classification comparable, costs are repacked to fixed cost (FC) and variable cost (VC) and are listed in Table 1.

To compare the cost composition in agricultural production in the US and China, there are some indices that are applied, including those in equation 34: average cost of production (C_i), average variable cost of production (C_i^0), fixed cost of land (C_i^1). Another three indices are average fixed cost of production (C_i^f), variable cost of land (C_i^v) and total cost of land (C_i^t). It can be noticed that costs averaged to unit production is named after 'average' with unit \$/t, while cost incurred from the unit area of land is within the total cost group with unit \$/km². Using these indices, variable cost and fixed cost (assigned to unit production or land, and the proportions are the same in either way) of the chosen crops of the US and China can be compared. Cost of the observed year is measured in dollar adjusted by domestic Consumer Purchasing Index (CPI, 2005=100).

Total cost of land C_i^t (\$/km²) for the four crops are generally high in the US, except wheat, of which China has a higher cost especially after 2008 (Figure 4). Cost of land is also different for crops as production of rice cost the most and soybean costs the least. Because of the associate difference in crop productivity (t/km²), average cost of

Table 1: Classification of production cost in China and the US

Cost type	China	US
Variable	Seed	Seed
	Fertilizer	Fertilizer
	Manure	Chemicals
	Plastic sheets	Custom operations
	Chemicals	Fuel, lube and electricity
	Machinery rent	Repairs
	Irrigation	Other variable expenses
	Animal power	Interest on operating inputs
	Fuel and electricity	Hired labour
	Technical services	Opportunity cost of unpaid labour
	Tools	
	Repairs	
	Other direct expenses	
	Hired labour	
	Self-employed labour	
Fixed	Depreciation of fixed assets	Capital recovery of machinery and equipment
	Taxes	Opportunity cost of land (rental rate)
	Insurance	Taxes and insurance
	Management	General farm overhead
	Financial activities	
	Sales	
	Land rental fees	

production C_i is similar between the US and China for production of maize and soybean, but is much higher for production of rice and wheat in the US (Figure 5). Average cost for unit production is low in maize and high in soybean.

Not only that the total cost or average cost is different between the two countries for different crops, their cost composition is also different. Looking at the proportion of variable cost and fixed cost, it is obvious that the proportion of fixed cost is higher in the US, while the opposite is for China (Figure 6). The average proportion of variable cost between 2004 and 2012 for rice has relative smaller difference, which is 63% in the US and 76% in China. For wheat it is 50% in the US and 82% in China. For maize, it is 57% in the US and 79% in China. For soybeans it is 41% in the US and 66% in China. Generally, the proportion of variable cost in these four crops are decreasing, except maize production in the US, and the decreasing is more obvious in China.

The exact fixed cost of land (C_i^1) is higher in the US for all the four crops and the difference is stable between the two countries Figure 7. The highest difference is in maize production, of which the fixed cost to a unit land area in the US is three time in average of China, followed by soybean, rice and wheat. However the difference is narrowing as the input of fixed out to land increases faster in China. The exact variable cost of land (C_i^v) is only obviously higher for rice in the US; the variable cost is much higher in China for wheat, and this gap between the two countries grows larger in the calculated period for wheat (Figure 8). Variable cost of land for maize is similar between the US and China, but the cost in China grows faster than that in the US. Variable cost of land for soybean is higher in China and the gap is also increasing.

Similarly, the exact cost valued in unit production also differs between the two countries. Fixed cost in unit production is higher for all four crops in the US (Figure 9, especially for the unit production of wheat, however the gap narrows as the fixed cost of unit production of wheat in China grows faster. Variable cost of unit production is higher in China except for rice (Figure 10), although the gap narrows as the variable cost grows faster in rice production in China. The cost difference is growing larger for the other three crops especially for soybean of which the variable cost in unit production grows also faster in China.

It is clear that difference cost compositions exist in a developing country and a developed country, which means that changes of prices of other input have different degree of impact on the crop production in different countries, considering their cost composition. According to the itemised cost in Table 1, primary crop production cost differs in crops and countries (Table 2). Compared to the US, labour seems always important in production cost, while in the US other input such as seed and energy may be more important.

Figure 4: Total cost of land for selected crops in China and the US

Table 2: Primary cost in crop production of China and the US

Crop	China		US	
	FC	VC	FC	VC
Wheat	Land rental rate	Labour	Capital recovery of machinery and equipment	Fertilizer
	Depreciation of fixed assets	Fertilizer		Land rental rate
Maize	Land rental rate	Labour	Capital recovery of machinery and equipment	Fertilizer
	Depreciation of fixed assets	Fertilizer		Land rental rate
Soybean	Land rental rate	Labour	Capital recovery of machinery and equipment	Seed
	Depreciation of fixed assets	Fertilizer		Land rental rate
Rice	Land rental rate	Labour	Capital recovery of machinery and equipment	Fuel, lube and electricity
	Depreciation of fixed assets	Fertilizer		Land rental rate

Figure 5: Average cost of production for selected crops in China and the US

Figure 6: Cost composition of selected crops in China and the US (in the order of China, the US of each year)

Figure 7: Fixed cost of land for selected crops in China and the US

Figure 8: Variable cost of land for selected crops in China and the US

Figure 9: Fixed cost of production for selected crops in China and the US

Figure 10: Variable cost of production for selected crops in China and the US

The above analysis is based on the geographical average, however it is very important the environmental conditions differs for suitable area of crop production, thus a profitable productivity is primarily affected by natural conditions as the potential productivity, with further management to get a real productivity. Therefore, productivity of a crop varied at different locations especially for countries covering different climatic zones. This productivity diversity if seen as in the gridded resolution, is the base for setting up a productivity distribution. Within limited survey, this variation in productivity can also be seen in Figure 11, which shows the the possible range of productivity in 2005 based on the surgery of major production provinces in China, and agricultural zones in the US.

4. Productivity distribution, cost distribution and region application

From the survey data in the US and China, we could assume that productivity across a geographical area is different due to variation in natural conditions and management, which can be reflected from the financial input. Natural conditions could not be very good for area where productivity is low, but the input to improve soil conditions, water provision and other management would be higher for these plots could be high to sustain this productivity. This can be seen from equation 34 where the inverse relationship between cost and productivity is possible in a geographical area where the diversity exists in natural conditions. The US survey data are actually based on the classification of agricultural zones with embedded natural factors. The Chinese data however are based on survey in major production provinces, but it also reflects geographical conditions although based on an administrative criteria (Figure 11).

Cost and productivity data of either the agricultural zones in the US or the administrative areas in China are panel data. Across each time section the paired cost-productivity of different area can be plotted in an x-y space. It is found that there is an inverse relationship between cost and productivity for each time section of the selected crops (Figure 12). If all the time sections are plotted, there would be a shift of the data towards higher cost and productivity. This time effect can be explained by the variations which can apply to each area similarly with change only in time, such as technology change. It is assumed that technology progresses usually at the national scale which

Figure 11: Different productivities of selected crops in the surveyed area of China and the US

applies generally equally to different regions. **Technology change contributes highly to the increasing of productivity in Chinese agriculture, especially the development in the nurturing of rice seeds.** It is therefore assumed that this time effect would apply to each area where a certain type of crop can be grown. The inverse relationship built upon limited geographical survey data are applied to grid points embedded in the LPJ-ml emulated of crop yield, which also represents geographical diversity described in model parameters. With the emulated crop yield and the built cost-productivity relationship, cost of crop production in each grid point of each region can be calculated.

Figure 12: Cost-productivity of crop production

Compared to other crops, this inverse relationship is relatively weak Japonica rice of China; however, this type of rice is not the only one produced in China. Indica rice is also widely grown in China. Chinese survey separates rice production to four types, namely Japonica rice, early Indica rice, Medium Indica rice and late Indica rice. Therefore when making approximation of the cost-productivity relation, all of the rice based on genetic types are considered, as they also represent geographical variations (Figure 12). There is also no apparent inverse relationship for the cost and productivity of rice in the US, because very few geographical locations are suitable for rice production, and these limited data are not enough to make a clear relation pattern. To make the transfer from productivity distribution space to cost distribution space available, the inverse relationship between cost and productivity for rice in the US is still assumed. For model estimation, time effect factor is applied to model of each year which modifies the intercept of the equation C_i^0 , and the decadal average represent an average time effect of the relationship. This factor is estimated for each time period, and interpolated to future period. Since the US survey can date back to the 1980s, a back-forecasting can be made to see whether this time-fixed effect model can explain the relationship between cost and productivity in the historical period. It is found that it is relatively good only for wheat. Therefore, in transferring productivity to cost distribution in a gridded area, adjustment based on price ratio between other crops to wheat can be applied instead of using the direct inverse relationship for a certain crop.

The estimated parameters of the intercept C_i^0 and coefficient C_i^1 for the base decadal 2005-2014 are listed in Table 3. LPJml emulator provide decadal crop productivity in each grid point ($0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$) with the base period of 2005-

2014. If a defined region is big enough to have multiple grids, the variation of productivity should follow a certain distribution (which will be discussed later). As the parameters in Table 3 are based on the geographical variation of productivity and cost, grid-based cost of each crop can be referred from this inverse relation to form a cost distribution. It should be noticed that the cost-productivity relationship is only based on data from China and the US, which can be taken as representatives of developing countries and developed country, but the exact cost must vary across countries; therefore applying to other countries will have bias. A possible correction way is to relate cost to price, as previously stated that production usually aims at making profit from controlling cost. Using the FAOstats yield and producer price (in dollar) data for separate countries and regions in the world, an inverse relationship can be found between producer price and yield for the selected crops (Figure 13), although the pattern is not strong for rice. Therefore the difference between cost can be interpreted to a certain extent with difference in producer price. In this way, the major countries and regions defined in the economic model E3ME are classified basically to two groups, either as a developing or a developed country/region according to the international Monetary Fund's World Outlook Report and World Bank data. It is assumed that production cost in a developed/developing country is proportional to production cost in the US/China with the ratio between their producer prices, and the composition of cost and the proportion of itemised fixed and variable cost is also the same to the US or China. The itemised cost in the US and China are extrapolated from 2013 to 2094 with a logarithm function to calculate their future proportions. The producer prices from 2000 to 2012 are provided by FAOstats for single crops and separate countries. Integrated price for a crop group is based on a production-weighted sum of single prices, which could be further integrated based on national production to produced a single price for a region, however, for simplicity a representative country in the region is used. Lack of a price for a single crop is gap-filled by prices of a similar crop.

Table 3: Nation-wide parameters of C_i^0 and C_i^1 for base period 2005-2014 (variable unit: \$/kg, \$/ha)

Crop	China		US	
	C_i^0	C_i^1	C_i^0	C_i^1
Wheat	0.12	504.4	0.14	224.8
Maize	0.06	737.8	0.05	760.1
Soybean	0.18	399.6	0.08	532.1
Rice	0.13	808.6	0.05	1408.4

Annual crop production based on the emulated productivity in LPJ-ml (converted from carbon content to weight of dry materials based according to Fader et al., 2010) and the related crop area do not match the FAOSTAT production data. As a result, the productivity trend from the base year 2010 to future (currently 2094) under climate change scenarios is obtained from the LPJ-ml emulator, but the base year productivity is adjusted from FAOSTAT production and LPJ-ml land use fraction map. A factor is then obtained as the ratio between the adjusted value and the emulated value. Since FAOSTAT has one average productivity for one crop in one country (for combination of crops and countries this single value is obtained through weighted productivity based on harvested area) and the emulated value is the regional weighted average based on single productivity at each grid point in a region and the area fraction the crop occupies.

This ratio is further applied to adjust the inverse of productivity (the land use intensity) when keeping the trend as well. We assume that the adjustment of productivity occurs to productivity value at each grid the same scale as the FAOSTAT average can supply, so the adjustment to the inverse of productivity at each grid is also the same so that only the weighted average of the inverse productivity is adjusted by applying the inverse of this ratio.

5. Discount rate for agricultural investment

Land use decisions made by farmers can be treated as investment activities. Whether to convert to other production or to keep the current one is base on the evaluation of profit in future. This is appraised in a capital budgeting procedure, e.g. net present value (NPV) analysis. Net present value is the difference between the present value of all returns and the present value of all cost associated with an investment. Whether it is positive or not decides whether an investment is desirable. Accordingly there are basically three parts: revenue, which is determined by commodity price and production quantity; cost, which is directed associated with the project; and discount rate, which reflect the

Figure 13: Price-productivity of global crop production

time preference and risk aversion of different farmers. Discounting the future value is an integral part of farmers' decision making processes, as they need to determine many production related investment including farm rotations, input choices, investment in machinery or structures, adoption of new technologies, and provision of environmental services (Duquette et al., 2011). This section provide a review of the discount rate choice in land use related projects, especially in agriculture, animal husbandry and forestry.

Usually an investment to agriculture such as purchasing of machines and land expansion for production happen at the beginning of a production period and the harvest of crops is related the growing period, therefore maximising profit does not apply, but the evaluation of present value of an expected future profit will be a reference for decision making. There are basically two schools in estimating social discount rate, the prescriptive and descriptive approaches. The former directly specifies a discount rate influenced by ethical principles and is usually advocated when projects affect future generations. The latter is based on the opportunity cost of capital used in the project and is based on efficiency criterion. Generally speaking, high discount rates are used in developing countries, and low discount rates are used in environmental applications as they impact more on future generations (references). Governments usually have recommended discount rates for advocated projects or public sectors. Other than governmental recommendations, individual economists and textbooks also give discount rates with very wide range from -3% to 27%. There is also a lower trend of discount rate in lots of countries (Table reference). Since there is no agreement on the choice of exact discount rate, sensitivity analysis should be conducted.

There is differences in the discount rate in the public and private sectors with an estimate of 3% to 5%. For social project, 4% is applied, and for private project, it is higher and can be up to 10%. (reference book). To approach the discount rate there are also variable ways which recommending it from 1 to 15%. For private sectors as there will be a risk aversion and individual selfishness the discount rate should be higher. This private individuals' preference to short-term, which is different from the long-term perspective of a social planner, is also related to constrained land management choices due to poverty. **However, as for some resource or environmental intensive projects, a public policy discount rate could reflect the societal value of the investment beyond investor, such as land use planning with or without consideration of environment conservation.** For the cost-benefit analysis of environmental projects, a real interest rate is used commonly as a universal agreement (Perman et al., 2003 in Gelaye, 2012). If the decision making is supposed to be made at individual level, such as a farmer, it is usually based on the subjective discount rate which reflect the risk averseness and individual time preference rate (Yemshanov, 2014). For application of new technologies there may be a risk premium rate applied.

Discount rates also varies across sectors reflecting differences in risk inherited in these sectors. For agricultural activities, the risk lays much on natural conditions and technology changes. Forestry usually has long-term project of which the discount rate for timber production could be 1%, although projects for forest conservation have much lower discount rate, perhaps 0.25% as it goes almost to infinity (Helliwell, 1974). When considering investment in land use, the time range for annual agricultural activities is different from ago-forestry systems, as the latter usually takes longer time. Accordingly some ways are also developed to deal with this long-term investment such as afforestation by using a decreasing discounting (Nijnik, 2014).

In reality, choice of discount rate with respect to natural resource economics is usually arbitrary. Some are referred from market rate of returner more specifically lending rate of financial institutions to reflect the private discount rate, others are social discount rate (Ballon, 2003), especially in developing countries where the private discount rate could be really high based on empirical evidence (Pearce, 2003). Determination of private discount rate can be a consumption rate of interest, which is based on the rate of time preference, or it can be based on an opportunity cost of the marginal productivity of capital (Pearce et al., 1990). If discount rate is defined as the marginal cost of money for a farm, it could imply that the interest rate could potentially be substituted for the discount rate. There is the assumption that each person's discount rate is equal to the rate of interest holds solely if the neoclassical conditions of perfect functioning markets, perfect information and no externalise are fulfilled (Fisher, 1930, Holder et al., 1998 in Kohlhasse, 2010). However, distortion of land and credit market could drive the discount rate up (Babier, 2003). If it is based on the consumption rate of interest, which is supposed by some as a better definition from a farmer's point of view in a financial analysis, then the economic status and attitude towards uncertainty and risks (as the time preference rate) influence the discount rate among individual farmers even when they face similar market interest (Hoekstra, 1985). Therefore, it has been argued that chronic poverty forces farmers to adopt a very short time horizon to realise the immediate economic despite resting the sustainability of their livelihoods (Adhikari, 2011). It is also argued that the rate of return from equity capital, and borrowing rate may be good indicators for analysing a commercial or semi-

commercial farming system in agroforestry systems, the consumption rate of interest will be more appropriate for the analysis on subsistence-oriented farms (Hoekstra, 1985). Since agricultural activities depend highly on the provision of natural resources such as soil and water, different attitudes towards the sustainability of these separate resources to keep an on-going productivity also lead to a diversion of time preference, thus social and private discount rate, besides the market distortion (Babier, 2003). That is to say, society will ascribe a higher value to future crop yields forgone due to resource exhaustion than will farmers. Another decision making in agriculture is the technology improvements, which although in a society as a whole is preferable to enhance the productivity of or provide substitutes for scarce factors, especially in a countries highly dependent on subsistence agriculture, is not treated of same value from a private perspective, as farms could always find alternatives for scare factors at a farm level (Babier, 2003).

Therefore, we could expect a relative narrow range of social discount rate, but few and more uncertain value of private discount rate in agriculture. Based on a literature review on the land-use related economic and financial analysis, mostly after 2000, both the social and the private discount has a very wide range globally (Figure 14). The social discount rates are higher than 2% and can be up to 15%. It is also obvious that social discount rates in developing countries are higher, with the highest discount rate for recorded developed countries just above 10%. Fewer information has been summarised for private discount rate, but still they are generally higher in the developing countries. A much wider range compared to social discount rates exists in private discount rates, due to some extreme values in some developing countries with values above 50% and even higher than 100%. Private discount rates in the developed countries only have limited data, but an in field experiment on farmers' attitude towards future provide 28% in the US. Generally social discount rates are lower than private discount rates. It is also obvious that in a country there is difference in choice of discount rates with regard to different regions and also specific projects, especially when it is chosen at the individual level. It should also be noticed that the choice of discount rate is sometimes related to the rotation period of land use. For example, afforestation usually is considered for a long-term which tends to have lower discount rate.

In some analysis both the social and private discounts are applied, so that it can be seen that there is difference both between the developed and developing countries, and between social and private discount rates (Figure 15).

Figure 14: Discount rates applied in certain projects.

Land-use systems have different production cycles, for example, annual crops has a production cycle of 1 year, for horticulture it is 5-6 years, and in timber plantation it is 12 years (Rasul, 2007). As a result, when comparing NPV between different land use system, a relatively long investment period is still needed. The choice of time horizons in the land use investment, especially when considering choices including forestry, will usually have a long period. Some in field experiment of detecting the private preference of future would assume short period of 3 months to 1

Figure 15: Social and private discount rates applied for a project in selected countries.

year, and the resulted farmers' individual discount rate can be above 50%. Choice of project time horizon can expand from one year to more than 100 years, considering types of land use including annual or perennial plantation, livestock husbandry, agroforestry, forest management as well as technique application for sustainability and conservation. These seems that for long-term projects the choice of discount rate in modelling or analysis are relatively small, especially in private discount rates (Figure 16).

6. Appendix: resources for discount rate

If not explained, the discount rates are all real discount rate (net of inflation).

Ethiopia, crops, 5%-50% (Shiferaw and Holden, 2001).

Australia, general land use change for environmental benefit, 5% (public) (Pannell, 2008).

Cameroon, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, land use change for tropical forest, 10%(32years), 8%(20,50years), 8%(100years); ecosystem change for developed countries, 2-3%, developing countries, 8-10%. (Turner et al., 2003).

Benin, land use conservation, 20% (Hoogeveen, 2003)

Philippines, timber to timber/crop mixed land, 15%, 20%, 8, 12 years (Bertomeu, 2006)

Thailand, low land agriculture conservation, 6%, 12%, 48 years. (Tiwari, 2000)

India, land use short rotation, 8% for individual, 5% for societal, 20years (Purushothaman, 2005)

Kenya, tree/crop preference, 10%, 10 years (Peralta 2009)

Ethiopia, farm, 24-36%, 7 and 10 years (Schmidt, 2014)

Pakistan, farm tree, 16%, 7 years (Shahid, 2002)

India, bamboo plantation, 8% farmer, 5.9% societal, 20 years (Pande, 2012)

Russian, forest management, 4% societal, 100years (Soloviy, 2009)

Finland, rotational forest timber, 3%, 30 years (Price, 2012)

US, saline land management, 6% ,45years(Characklis, 2005)

Bangladesh, land use system change, 12%, 12 years (Rasul, 2007)

Malawi, soil fertility management, 2-5%, societal (?)

US, alfalfa farm, 2.3% 1980's (Schooner, 1983)

Mexico, farmer's forest management, 10%, 100 years (Jong, 2000)

Vietnam, farmer's choice to afforest, 6%, 12%, 15%, 8 years(Nguyen, 2010)

Australia, forestry investment, 7%, 30 years(Venn, 2005)

Figure 16: Choice of discount rates and time horizon in analysis.

Some extreme annual mean discount rates in the developing countries such as Indonesia (93%), Zambia (105%), Ethiopia (53%) and India (50%). This high time preference is said to be related to the high-risk environment faced by the farmers, such as frequent climatic disasters, crop price fluctuations and health risk in the production environment. Ethiopia, conservation of cloud forest, 30% is the average discount rate under which conversion to crop is reasonable; discount rate lower than 30% facilitate sustainable forest management, 40 years (Reichbuher, 2012)

Ethiopia, degraded forest management, 9.86%, 21 years (Tilahun, 2007)

Ethiopia, forest enclosures or not, 8% (social time preference), 30 years (Balana, 2012)

Spain, dry land cereal to forest or not, 4%, 80-120 years (Ovando, 2010)

Thailand, tropical forest management, 10%, 5 years (Albers, 2007)

Ireland, public forestry, 5% (government recommended, because the discount rate used to evaluate public projects is chosen via the political system in practice), 35 years (Clinch, 2000)

Uruguay, reforestation in marginal land, 6%, 16 years (social discount rate) (Olmos, 2007)

New Zealand, land use change, 4-10% (social discount rate), 28 years (Dodd, 2008)

USA, forest management, annual average 3.7% (social?), beyond 45 years (the maturity period) (Gutrich, 2007)

A review about forestry in India: Choice of discount rate with respect to natural resource economics is usually arbitrary. Some are referred from the market rate of return or more specifically lending rate of financial institutions to reflect the private discount rate, others are social discount rate (Balloon, 2003).

Lebanon, adaptation technology in agriculture, 6%, 10 years (?) (Trarup, 2014)

Bolivia, forestry, deforestation, 0-25% (?), sensitivity, 10 years (Davies, 2000)

Some ways to deal with long-term investment regarding afforestation: a decreasing discounting (Nijnik, 2014).

Whether using financial discounting or social discounting is not solved in decision of resource involved projects, and the discount rate is not clear for developing countries of which it can be very high (Pearce, 2003).

Choice of discount rate sometimes is that the choice of consumption decide behaviour of producer, so it is a societal point of view to whether be willing to pay for all the cost rather than from an individual point. More concept on DR in (Requier, 2011).

'Discounting the future value is an integral part of farmers' decision making processes (Duquette, Higgis, and Horowitz, 2011)', also in this paper: American farmer, 28%; Kenya, 10%, this paper for Bhutan's land use management, 25%, 6 years (Nkonya, 2014).

Individual time preference rate is different from that of the applied consumers' sovereignty of the CBA, and this needs

data about the behaviour of households on capital markets.

Canada, land use, 4%, 55 years (Yemshanov, 2014).

China, livestock systems, 5%, 25 years (carbon emission abatement) (Koslowski, 2012)

New Zealand, sheep farming, 5%, 5 years (Kaye-Blake, 2008)

‘The discount rate can be defined as the marginal cost of money for a farm for which the analysis is being done. This would imply that the interest rate could potentially be substituted for the discount rate. However, structural problems in the financial industry limit the access of credit to dryland users, thereby driving up the discount rate. Also, factors such as the current economic status, and attitude toward risk and uncertainty influence the discount rate among individual farmers...It has been argued that chronic poverty forces farmers to adopt a very short time horizon to realise the immediate economic effects despite risking the sustainability of their livelihoods. However, although farmers strive to fulfil their short-term needs, rural communities make a significant investment in terms of money and time to improve the future of their children and are not entirely guided by short-term thinking.’ (Adhikari, 2011)

US, forest restoration, 7% (federal rate), 60 years (Talberth, 2009)

‘A discount rate can be a consumption rate of interest, which is based on time preference, or it can be based on an opportunity cost of the marginal productivity of capital. Discounting is an important issue in environmental management, because the effects are long-lived and have benefits that occur far in the future...’ (Parviainen, 2012)

Details about discounting in natural resources and generations. (van Kooten, 2014).

China, sustainable forestry, 12% (social?), 20 years (World bank, 2002)

Ghana, forestry, 15% (social?), 5 years (all types of crops as lost because of deforestation) (Damnyag, 2012)

General Latin America, forestry, 10% (financial), 15 years (Pavez, 2014) [Explanation of discount rate](#)

Cameroon, agroforestry technology, 20% (financial), 5 years (Degrande, 2005)

Australia, wetland management, 7% (social?), 30 years (Whitten, 2001)

Although the choice of the (social) discount rate for CBA of environmental projects remains controversial, there is a universal agreement among economists that a real interest rate, which is the nominal interest rate adjusted for inflation, has to be used (Perman et al., 2003) (Gelaye 2012)

‘As discussed by Barbier (2003), a farmer’s discount rate may be affected by the pure time preference rate, reflecting his attitude to risk and uncertainty as well as the level of household poverty, and the marginal opportunity cost of capital, which represent the scarcity value of savings and returns to alternative investments.’ (Bekele, 2003)

‘Section 2.2’ (Kohlhase, 2011)

Indian village, 30-60% (Pender, 1996); Ethiopia, in field experiment, 3 month (105%), 6 month (58%, 63%), 12 month (43%) (Yesuf and Bluffstone, 2008); Used in analysis of forestry of carbon emission reduction, 10% for China, Indonesia, Mexico, Tanzania, Brazil; 12% for India, Philippines; 18% (private), Brazil; 6%, India environmental projects. (Stacey, 2001); (30 years projects)

A number of studies have used discount rates ranging between 3 and 6% in real terms to evaluate afforestation projects (social, Ninan, 2001); World bank recommends 12% social discount for project appraisals in developing countries (Ninan, 2001); Vietnam, choice to reduce land degradation, 15 years, 5% (social), 20% (private); (Clayton, 2003);

Canada, 4%, 20 years, boreal afforestation (Lempriere, 2013); Indonesia, land use system choice, 8% (private), 3% (social), 35 years (Sofiyuddin); Kenya, genomic tools in crops, 22 years, 20% (private), 3% (social) (Komirenko, 2014); UK, forestry, 49/59 years, 3.5% (social), 7% (private), (Nijnik, 2009); Philippines, longer than 10 years, forestry, 12 to 18% (social) (Harrison, 2000); US, tillage adoption, 4% (social, 50 years), 12% (private, 50 years) (Baradi, 2005); Australia, salinity control, 6% (social), 10% (private), 15 years (Ullah, 2001); Sri Lanka, 10% (private), 30 years, soil conservation application (Ananda, 2001); Vietnam, choice to fruit tree agroforestry and soil conservation, 10% (social), 12% (private), 30 years (The, 2001); Sudan, age up to 20 years, choice of gum arabic agroforestry or crops, 19%, 36% and 53% (Rahim, 2007); Finland, fertiliser application, 5% (social), 9% (private), 10-15 years (Iho, 2010); Philippines, forestry vs crop, 5.7% (social), 11.4% (private), 15 years (Martin, 2011); Indonesia, oil palm plantation, 15% (social), 20% (private), 25 years (Papenfus, 2000); Australia, landscape investment, 3-8% (social, country), 4, 7, 10% (social, NSW); 13% (private), 100 years (Hajkowicz, 2005);

7. Appendix: some notes about representation of policy in FTT: Agriculture

When creating policy scenarios both the qualitative part (as the story line) and the quantitative part (which is for model representation) should be considered. Regional policies are trailered to a certain scale so a global policy scenario needs generalisation from regional difference to represent most urgent or hot policy debate. ‘A considerable challenge was downscaling land-use assumptions of the global-scale IPCC SRES to a suitable scale for regional assessment’ (Sohl2013). A scenario framework could have several dimensions representing both direct and indirect land policy. The direct policies includes policies closely related to land use types which are represented in the model; the indirect ones include policies applying to sectors other than for example agriculture, forestry or natural reserve, Policy scenarios should capture recent up to 2050 developments concerning mainly global policy development. Scenarios should also be comparable to the major story lines consistent in global modelling, and the those applied in other FTT series of energy and transport. e.g. Economics vs Environment.

From the position of land use model in the whole model components, FTT: agriculture takes parameters from biophysical model which is resulted also from circulation model. It provides impacts from land use conversion such as deforestation on physical environment. Policies of land use should represent impacts of land use change through the model linkage (model components and parameters taking respective feedbacks such as price, climate, water).

Global scenario analyses indicate that key ”drivers” for future land use will be the **agricultural production systems** (under trend of business-as-usual unto 2050), especially the food-feed system [citation]. Model finding of food/feed and respective land use are well understood and robust, with major uncertainty coming from the development of demands for agricultural/forest products and trends in yields of different cultivation systems subject to climate feedback, and this usually leads to net area expansion and internal transformation between cropland and pasture [citation]. There is always inverse relations between agricultural and forest land; gains in overall forest land in boreal and temperate climates and loss in savannahs and warmer forest can be significant; land use change will be uneven between industrialised, developing and emerging countries as well as geographically; bioenergy and (biofuels) would have significant regional impacts especially in tropical countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America and Southeast Asia although as a minor driving factor [citation]. **Land-use planning to avoid negative environmental consequences of land use while sustaining the production of essential resources.**

Change in assumption of yield change would bring impacts on land use, and changes in the demand side such as diet change would bring far more reduction in land use [citation]. From the demand side, food and bioenergy policies should be important in the land policy frame.

Land use should be treated as a global issue although regional land use policies may target to different local issues. A global view comes from the close linkage in world economy and the boundless climate change. Therefore national land use related policies should be embedded in international policies, which can be represented by international treaties affecting global food production and distribution; environmental treaties relevant to land use and conversion, climate change convention and convention on biodiversity; local land use impact can also accumulated to have impact beyond local level to impact global environment, for most through climate change [Schneider2011].

Examples of scenario analysis to address the impact of different policies on land-use, food security and environmental change based on combinations of socio-economic and biophysical issues (see Arets2011):

1. The OECD Environmental Outlook to 2030
2. IAASTD, 2009
3. ten Brink et al, 2010

Possible scopes:

1. Agricultural change and land practice (for potential yield and ecosystem services):
 - (a) agricultural support and trade policies (subsidies/protectionism vs. open trade); deficiency payments or farm subsidies (Fuel Versus Food); food priority as land can be largely converted to cropland (Akhtar2013)
 - (b) encouragement in agriculture technology, water use efficiency, soil protection; intensification or extensification of agriculture; subsidies for fertiliser or water; prioritised crop types;
 - (c) compulsory ‘set-aside’ regulations; encouragement for converting cropland for ecosystem services, afforestation (credit vs tax if forest taken to cropping, should provide exact value of money e.g Radeloff2011); could have different strictness, such tax only applied to forest→crop, or to all other converted use (Lawler2005).

(d) Some words from American policies (POLICY GUIDE ON PLANNING & CLIMATE CHANGE): (LUpolicy13) support agricultural land uses including forestry through agricultural zoning regulations, preservation easements and incentives. Support local food and local biofuel production initiatives. Assist farmers with implementation of best management practices for CO₂ and other GHG sequestration and management; (NRpolicy2) Establish educational programs and incentives to promote agricultural cultivation and livestock best management practices that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and that allow the sequestration potential of agricultural activities to be realised; (NRpolicy4) Protect agricultural lands from urban and suburban encroachment.

(e)

2. environmental policies
3. Too far? population control (age structure? distribution? education? labour price?), possibly beyond parameters in FTT: agriculture; scenarios represented by parameters input into other modules?
4. urbanisation policies (urban agriculture); rural development related agri-envi conservation;
5. food policies: avoid food waste, diet change; self-sufficiency (in E3ME?)
6. climate mitigation policies (carbon policies): pricing carbon emission from land or credit carbon uptake on land
7. energy policies: trade barriers on the biofuel market (tariff of import and tax credit for domestic production); regional biofuel policies such as mandatory blending of policies in US or EU;

Possible **baseline** (Kraxner2012): Land use change will happen due to:

1. demands for food, fiber and fuel due to global population growth
2. no restriction on forest use (continuation of historical forest clearance)

Assumptions go with baselines:

1. Population growth and per capita GDP unto 2050
2. demand driven by E3ME setting (population, GDP)?
3. productivity trend set
4. diet set
5. ...

Alternative policy scenarios have to make certain aspects competitive to Baseline.

Note:

1. Adaption vs mitigation policies?
2. Scenario analysis: so-called 'what-if' analysis.
3. policies targeted to financial support for agricultural practices rather than direct subsidizing food and fibre production
4. An example of 'regional agricultural policy scenario' in (Angus2009)
5. The distinctness of policies: agricultural policy, environmental policy (main driving force for UK land use)
6. Global target for sustainability requires a balance of policy driven goals and market forces. It is possible in policy scenario design that environmental policies related to land use might be more suitable than direct intervention of food/fuel market (Angus2009).
7. Policies directly targeting to ecosystem vs. agricultural policies (on management to combat degradation etc. (Stoate2009))
8. Some local policies are too detailed to be globally simulated (Bell2010). Combination of policies addressing to a target that will impact production and land use (Hart2013).
9. Scenarios can be applied as a shock or gradually implemented (Schmitz2011).
10. Scenarios have different degree of intensification of land use (Hallgren2012).
11. Policy scenarios may take effect from applying to E3ME: carbon tax/production subsidies/urban growth (probably not, as this can be constrained in land conversion direction)?
12. Policy scenarios should be 'designed to represent ambitious but potentially plausible policies that have already been implemented in some areas' (Hamilton2013). If policies are internationally applicable?

13. How to represent land quality protection?
14. Tax/subsidies applied to affect production cost, details in setting tax? (Mann2012)
15. No value judgement or any ecosystem value things, just suggest what is applicable in policy, e.g. try and find a suitable price in simulation.
16. Policy scenarios should address questions like ‘what is the suitable tax level to stop deforestation? and it may also help to find sensitivity of land use conversion to price/policies.(Upadhyay2013)’
17. What is general policy scenario as targeting to a main topic such as emission reduction that has been represented in detail in each FTT sector?
18. consistency in a series of policy scenarios among different sectors.

Acknowledgements

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